

Proposal for the EOSC Semantic Interoperability Questionnaire

Supplementary material for the paper:

Converging towards a Semantic Interoperability Framework for EOSC: understanding the different community solutions

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Glossary:

In this glossary, terms are defined as discussed between the authors of the paper only for the purpose of this questionnaire without any claim of completeness or consensus within EOSC SI TF.

Crosswalk: set of rules that defines how (meta)data elements or attributes (i.e., slots) from one schema or format can be aligned and mapped to (meta)data elements or attributes in another schema or format that share the same constraints and thus share the same semantic role (as defined in the main paper).

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

FAIR Supporting Resource (FSR): a resource used by a community to facilitate the process of FAIRification of (meta)data and ultimately also semantic interoperability.

Machine actionability: machine-interpretable bit sequences for which operations have been specified in symbolic grammar such as logical reasoning for OWL-based (meta)data and other rule-based operations.

Metadata Schema: A schema is a logical plan showing the relationships between metadata elements, normally through establishing rules for the use and management of metadata specifically as regards the semantics, the syntax and the optionality (obligation level) of values (based on ISO 23081.1 Terms and Definitions)

Nanopublication: is a specific form of machine-readable information that represents small, self-contained units of information. It is typically structured using standardised formats expressed in RDF (Research Description Format) and Named Graphs.

Semantic artefact: a machine-actionable formalisation of a conceptualisation enabling sharing and reuse by humans and machines. These artefacts may have a broad range of formalisation, from a loose set of terms, taxonomies, thesauri to higher-order logics, and include the concepts/terms/classes constituting these. Moreover, semantic artefacts are serialised using a variety of digital representation formats, e.g., RDF Turtle, OWL-RDF, XML, JSON-LD (Le Franc et al., 2022). The SI Task Force discussed whether metadata schemas could be considered as semantic artefacts. It was agreed that this is true only when they are machine readable which is not always the case. For this reason and also because the FAIR Principles explicitly refer to those concepts separately because metadata needs to use vocabularies to be FAIR, it was decided to provide separate definitions for both terms.

Semantic Interoperability (SI): the ability of computer systems to transmit data with unambiguous, shared meaning... It ensures that the precise format and meaning of exchanged data and information is preserved and understood throughout exchanges between parties. In other words, 'what is sent is what is understood (Corcho et al., 2021).

Semantic Interoperability Profile (SIP): a list of FAIR Supporting Resources chosen by a community to support semantic interoperability of (meta)data.

Term mapping: Mappings of terms defined in different semantic artefacts sharing the meaning and identifying the same referent (i.e., the object designated by the term).

References

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